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Dolby Atmos-Based Recording and Spatial Audio Production Approaches for Turkish Folk Music¹

Türk Halk Müziği için Dolby Atmos Tabanlı Kayıt ve Uzamsal Ses Üretimi Yaklaşımları

ABSTRACT

This study aims to bring together the traditional performance practices of Turkish Folk Music (TFM) with contemporary audio technologies by examining the recording and spatial mixing process of the anonymous Erzurum folk song “*Uyan Sunam*” in the Dolby Atmos format. The primary objective of the research is to reveal how traditional instruments such as the bağlama, cura, kaval, and various percussion instruments can be represented aesthetically and technically within a three-dimensional sound field. To this end, multichannel microphone techniques, the use of height channels, object-based mixing approaches, and spatial placement strategies are discussed in detail. The possibilities offered by spatial audio technologies not only create an expanded auditory space but also provide a more immersive listening experience that aligns with the collective, participatory, and spatial characteristics of Turkish Folk Music. Within the scope of this study, a 15-question survey was designed to understand preferences between stereo and Atmos audio formats. At this stage of the process, face-to-face interviews were conducted with participants who listened to the mixes. A total of 41 individuals, comprising bağlama performers, Turkish Folk Music performers, audio engineers, academics, and students, were asked questions regarding the prepared TFM Atmos mix. The results for each question were grouped and analyzed according to common themes. In addition, the data obtained through SPSS analysis and their interpretations are summarized at the end of the study. The main outcome of this research is to present perceptual evaluations alongside technical ideas and approaches that can be utilized in future Atmos audio engineering studies. The findings indicate that Dolby Atmos can preserve the timbral richness of traditional instruments while offering a perspective that positions the listener at the center of the performance. This study demonstrates that modern audio technologies have the potential to make significant contributions to the contemporary reinterpretation of a culturally rooted musical genre such as Turkish Folk Music, opening up new areas of research from both creative and aesthetic perspectives.

Keywords: Dolby Atmos, Spatial Audio, Turkish Folk Music, Recording and Production, Object-Based Mixing.

ÖZET

Bu çalışma, anonim Erzurum türküsü “Uyan Sunam”ın Dolby Atmos formatında kayıt ve mekânsal mikşaj sürecini inceleyerek Türk Halk Müziği (THM)nin geleneksel icra pratiklerini çağdaş ses teknolojileriyle bir araya getirmeyi amaçlamaktadır. Araştırmanın temel amacı, bağlama, cura, kaval ve çeşitli vurmalı çalgılar gibi geleneksel enstrümanların üç boyutlu bir ses alanı içerisinde estetik ve teknik açıdan nasıl temsil edilebileceğini ortaya koymaktır. Bu doğrultuda, çok kanallı mikrofon teknikleri, yükseklik kanallarının kullanımı, nesne tabanlı mikşaj yaklaşımları ve mekânsal yerleştirme stratejileri ayrıntılı olarak ele alınmaktadır. Mekânsal ses teknolojilerinin sunduğu imkânlar, yalnızca genişletilmiş bir işitsel alan yaratmakla kalmamakta, aynı zamanda Türk Halk Müziği’nin kolektif, katılımcı ve mekânsal özellikleriyle uyumlu, daha içine alan bir dinleme deneyimi de

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sağlamaktadır. Bu çalışma kapsamında, stereo ve Atmos ses formatları arasındaki tercihleri anlamak amacıyla 15 soruluk bir anket tasarlanmıştır. Sürecin bu aşamasında, miksleri dinleyen katılımcılarla yüz yüze görüşmeler gerçekleştirilmiştir. Hazırlanan THM Atmos mikisine ilişkin sorular, bağlama icracıları, Türk Halk Müziği icracıları, ses mühendisleri, akademisyenler ve öğrencilerden oluşan toplam 41 kişiye yöneltilmiştir. Her bir soruya ait sonuçlar ortak temalara göre gruplandırılarak analiz edilmiştir. Ayrıca, SPSS analizi ile elde edilen veriler ve bunlara ilişkin yorumlar çalışmanın sonunda özetlenmektedir. Bu araştırmanın başlıca çıktısı, gelecekteki Atmos ses mühendisliği çalışmalarında kullanılacak teknik fikir ve yaklaşımların yanı sıra algısal değerlendirmeleri de ortaya koymaktır. Bulgular, Dolby Atmos'un, dinleyiciyi icranın merkezine yerleştiren bir perspektif sunarken geleneksel enstrümanların tınısal zenginliğini koruyabildiğine işaret etmektedir. Bu çalışma, modern ses teknolojilerinin, Türk Halk Müziği gibi kültürel olarak köklü bir müzik türünün çağdaş yeniden yorumlanmasına kayda değer katkılar sunma potansiyeline sahip olduğunu ve hem yaratıcı hem de estetik açılardan yeni araştırma alanları açtığını ortaya koymaktadır.

Anahtar kelimeler: Dolby Atmos, Uzamsal Ses, Türk Halk Müziği, Ses Kaydı ve Prodüksiyonu, Nesne Tabanlı Miks.

1. INTRODUCTION

Turkish Folk Music (TFM) is a deep-rooted musical tradition that embodies Türkiye's oral culture, collective memory, and regional diversity. Today, rapid advancements in digitalisation and sound technologies have reshaped the recording and production practices of traditional music. In particular, spatial audio technologies that extend beyond the conventional stereo format offer new possibilities that transform musical expression. Research on the spatial perception of sound highlights the directional sensitivities of human hearing and the psychophysical foundations of the three-dimensional soundstage, emphasizing the decisive role of spatial auditory experience in shaping musical impact (Blauert, 1997; Rumsey, 2012).

The historical and technical literature on spatial audio production and multichannel techniques demonstrates the emergence of new approaches within both recording and mixing processes. Boren (2017) explains how immersive formats have broadened musical production through an overview of the historical development of multichannel and 3D sound, while Lee (2021) emphasises the critical importance of multichannel 3D microphone arrays in capturing spatial information during recording sessions. Comprehensive studies on microphone techniques by Eargle (2012) and Huber and Runstein (2005) provide detailed examinations of stereo, multichannel, and surround microphone configurations. In addition, Brixen (n.d.) demonstrates the effects of various stereo configurations on spatial depth and soundstage width. Finally, Rumsey and McCormick (2006) delineate the technical and auditory foundations of the modern audio recording chain, establishing a conceptual framework for the essential components of spatial audio production.

Object-based formats such as Dolby Atmos enable each sound source to be defined within three-dimensional auditory space through parameters including location, movement, and volume. Owing to their capacity to construct a fully immersive 3D soundfield around the listener, these formats possess strong potential to significantly transform the experience of traditional music. The ability to assign positional, directional, amplitude, and temporal attributes to each object provides Atmos with notable technical advantages (Hannah, 2021). The structural incorporation of height channels, bed-object differentiation, and spatial parameter control further illustrate the technological possibilities that Atmos provides for musical production.

Considering the distinctive timbre and directional sound projection of traditional Turkish Folk Music instruments such as bağlama, cura, and kaval, their representation within a three-dimensional soundstage constitutes an important area of technical research. Indeed, Tarıkçı's (2012) study on bağlama recording techniques demonstrates the extent to which microphone strategies are decisive in capturing the accurate and natural timbre of such instruments.

There is still only a limited number of studies in the literature that extensively examine the recording and spatial remixing of Turkish Folk Music in an object-based format such as Dolby Atmos. However, the historical development of even home audio playback systems demonstrates that listening habits are continually evolving and that spatial audio formats are increasingly becoming standard (Önen, 2018). This situation highlights the necessity of repositioning traditional musics within contemporary auditory aesthetics.

This study addresses this gap by examining the multichannel microphone recording, use of height channels, and object-based mixing techniques employed in the Dolby Atmos production of the piece "Uyan Sunam." The aim of the research is to demonstrate how Turkish Folk Music instruments can be aesthetically and technically represented within a three-dimensional soundstage. Its objective is to propose an original and applicable spatial production approach that can be implemented in both the recording and

mixing stages. In this respect, the study offers a unique contribution not only to the spatial audio literature but also to the contemporary re-evaluation of Turkish Folk Music through advanced audio technologies.

Regarding materials and methods, this research employs multichannel recording and Dolby Atmos mixing techniques to reproduce the Turkish Folk Music piece “Uyan Sunam” in a spatial audio format. The research material consists of bağlama, cura, kaval, classical guitar, bass guitar, and various percussion performances, along with the multilayered audio recordings obtained from these performances. Methodologically, a three-dimensional recording approach was adopted that combined close and ambient microphone techniques and incorporated height channels. The data were recorded in Dolby Atmos-certified studios at Istanbul Technical University Center for Advanced Studies in Music (İTÜ MİAM), after which a spatial soundstage was designed through a bed- and object-based mixing workflow. The materials and methods used are explained in detail in the following sections under separate subheadings.

2. RESEARCH ENVIRONMENT AND TECHNICAL INFRASTRUCTURE

This study was conducted with the aim of recording the Turkish Folk Music piece “Uyan Sunam” in a spatial audio format and mixing it within a Dolby Atmos environment. The recording and mixing processes were carried out in Dolby Atmos-certified studios at the Istanbul Technical University Center for Advanced Studies in Music (İTÜ MİAM).

Figure 1. Front view of the control room in the studio

Two studios were utilised in this study. The larger one, the Main Recording and Mixing Studio, is equipped with a 7.1.4 configuration of ATC loudspeakers, including the SCM 200, SCM 150, and SCM 20 models, and its calibration was carried out by Dolby (See Figure 1, Figure 2 and Figure 3).

Figure 2. Rear View of the Studio Control Room

Figure 3. Height Speakers in the Studio Listening and Mixing Room

The second studio, designed solely for mixing, is the Video 1 Atmos Room. It features a 7.1.4 system composed of Adam Audio T5V monitors, which are more suitable for small to medium-sized studio spaces, and the system has likewise been calibrated by Dolby (See Figure 4).

Figure 4. The general view of the Video 1 Atmos Room

3. EQUIPMENT AND SOFTWARE USED

During the recording process, the industry-standard Pro Tools Ultimate digital audio workstation, operating through an HDX card system, was used (See Figure 5). For AD/DA conversion in the main studio system, an Apogee Symphony interface was employed. All production stages were carried out at a resolution of 24-bit / 48 kHz.

Grace 801 preamplifiers were preferred for their transparent sonic character, which does not color the signal. During the recording sessions, Beyerdynamic DT 770 headphones were provided to the musicians.

Figure 5. Pro Tools Mixer Interface

Microphone selections were diversified according to the instrument and recording purpose; cardioid microphones were used for close-miking, whereas omnidirectional microphones were used for ambient capture. The Neumann U87 was chosen for its large-diaphragm condenser design, while the Neumann KM184 was preferred due to its bright, detailed sonic character and its ability to capture fast transients with clarity. To record the room acoustics with a natural and wide stereo image, a DPA 4006 stereo omnidirectional set was utilised. In addition, the Audix D6 was selected for low-frequency percussion instruments because of its strong bass response, and a Radial J48 DI box was utilized to deliver a clean, noise-free, and lossless signal transfer for the bass guitar.

4. MICROPHONING APPROACH AND SPATIAL RECORDING DESIGN

For spatial audio production, the study was designed using a multilayered microphone strategy aimed at achieving three-dimensional soundstage depth. Room microphones were positioned on both horizontal and vertical axes, and additional microphone arrays were implemented to integrate height (vertical) channels into the Atmos mix (See Figure 6).

Figure 6. Vertical and Horizontal Stereo Room Microphones and Close Mono Microphone

4.1. Room Microphone Technique

In this study, an approach inspired by the OCT-3D technique, a microphone placement method used for multichannel and three-dimensional audio recording, was implemented to enhance traditional stereo recording methods. OCT-3D operates with three main capsules accompanied by lateral support microphones. Its purpose is to capture a natural 3D spatial impression by providing both a wide stereo field and a sense of height, offering realistic localisation and depth suitable for spatial systems such as Atmos. Therefore, in addition to the traditional stereo AB recording technique, height channels inspired by the OCT-3D structure were incorporated into the recording setup used in this study.

To accurately capture both room acoustics and high-level spatial reflections appropriate for Atmos mixing, two separate structures were implemented: a horizontal AB stereo omni set aimed toward the sound source, placed parallel to the ground, spaced 50 cm apart, positioned 150 cm above the floor and 200 cm from the source, using a DPA 4006 stereo set; and a vertical cardioid microphone pair positioned toward the ceiling, spaced 50 cm apart, placed 250 cm above the floor and 260 cm from the source, using a Neumann KM184 stereo set.

4.2. Close Microphone Technique

Close-miking techniques were applied to each instrument in order to capture their timbral characteristics and direct sound components. In order to take greater advantage of the expanded soundstage offered by Dolby Atmos, all instrumental parts were recorded four times. This approach enabled the distribution of sound sources across different height and positional channels during the mixing stage, allowing the three-dimensional spatial placement to be constructed in a more flexible and controlled manner. This method provided detailed localisation possibilities compatible with the multilayered surround structure of the Atmos format.

4.3. Performance and Tracking Configuration

The bağlama parts were recorded using a Neumann U87 at a distance of 80 cm, with four takes performed in the first octave (See Figure 7). The cura parts were also recorded with a Neumann U87 placed 30 cm from the instrument, with four takes performed in the second octave (See Figure 8). Percussion instruments such as bendir, cajon, and djembe were captured in two separate partitions, with two channels assigned to each (See Figure 9). Both the classical guitar and the kaval were recorded from two different microphone positions, with four takes captured for each position. Each ornamental percussion element, including shaker, shell percussion, brush bendir, bowed drum, and chimes, was recorded as four separate channels. Vocals were recorded using a CAD VX2 tube microphone, with three layered tracks comprising a main vocal line, a main vocal an octave lower, and a third-interval backing vocal.

Figure 7. Bağlama Recording Process

5. RECORDING WORKFLOW

The recording process, carried out over four days with five musicians, began with the bağlama and vocal performances being recorded to a metronome to serve as a reference. Following this, the main rhythm group (bendir, cajón, and djembe) was recorded. Based on this rhythmic foundation, the bağlama, cura, kaval, and classical guitar parts were subsequently recorded as four-channel layers in accordance with the Atmos production design.

Figure 8. Cura Recordings

After the bass guitar and all additional supporting percussion recordings were completed, the vocal tracks were recorded, concluding the process.

Figure 9. Bendir Recording: Cross and Front Angle View

6. MIXING METHOD AND SPATIAL PLACEMENT

The mixing process was carried out in Pro Tools, where both bed and object structures were created within the Dolby Atmos environment. The approach aimed to provide spatial width while preserving the natural timbre of Turkish Folk Music, without excessively altering traditional stage perception.

The following visuals present 3D spatial placement maps that illustrate how the sounds were positioned within the Atmos mix (See Figure 10, Figure 11, Figure 12). The central point represents the reference location of the listener.

Figure 10. Top View of the Dolby Atmos Bağlama and Cura Channels

The green dots distributed around the listener, represented by a human head figure, indicate the different audio channels used in the mix. Some channels are positioned in height locations, while others are designed within room-based or surround placements.

Figure 11. Rear View of Some Dolby Atmos Percussion Channels

Since placing every sound source into a single visual representation would have produced an overly complex image, the audio material was distributed across multiple grouped visual layouts.

In the mix, the bass guitar and low-frequency percussion were positioned at the physical center, while the main vocal was placed at the stereo center. As a general approach, high-frequency instruments such as cura, chimes, and shaker were assigned to the height channels, whereas bass-oriented instruments were positioned on the lower plane (See Figure 11).

Figure 12. Side View of Some Dolby Atmos Percussion Channels

To maintain a natural sense of spatial perception, dynamic panning was avoided, and intentional movement was minimized. For reverb processing, LiquidSonics Cinematic Rooms (3D version) was selected. It is an advanced 3D reverb tool developed to create natural, immersive, and cinematic spatial environments in Atmos and binaural mixes, and is commonly used in film, television, and music production. Offering control over three-dimensional stage depth, height, and width, this reverb strengthens the spatial perception of the mix and provides realistic room, hall, and cinematic ambience responses.

After the completion of the mix, the piece was exported in ADM-BWF format, which is the delivery standard for Dolby Atmos projects. Additionally, a traditional two-channel stereo mix (left and right) maintaining the same balance, and a binaural mix designed for headphone listening, creating a 3D spatial perception within two channels, were rendered. Sennheiser HD 600 headphones were used for the binaural listening process.

7. SURVEY AND STATISTICAL EVALUATION

In this study, a qualitative research approach was employed to examine the effects of Dolby Atmos, stereo, and binaural formats on listener perception. Participants were invited to the studio individually, where each was given the opportunity to listen to the piece in all three formats, and subsequently asked to complete an evaluation survey. Surveys were conducted with 41 participants, and in addition, face-to-face in-depth interviews were held with 12 experts from the industry and academia.

The research data were obtained through the evaluation of a structured interview and survey form consisting of 15 questions, including personal information and listening assessment items. The participants who listened to the mixes were given a survey containing Likert-type response scales and multiple-choice questions designed to measure their perceptual responses. Additionally, semi-structured, in-depth interviews were conducted with academics and professional musicians, during which detailed feedback was collected regarding technical, emotional, and perceptual aspects of the mix.

The Likert-scale responses to the question “How would you evaluate your listening experience of the production in Atmos?” demonstrate that the Atmos production was highly appreciated by the listeners. The high score distribution, where there were over 95% positive responses with a mean score of 4.54, indicates that the production provided a highly successful listening experience, while negative feedback remained minimal (See Figure 13).

Figure 13. Evaluation of listening experience

The data further reveal that the use of height channels, as well as the lateral and rear spatial perception in the bağlama and percussion sound design within the Atmos production, was considered technically and aesthetically successful and was widely appreciated by the listeners.

The elements that most strongly impressed listeners in the Atmos production were the spatial audio experience, along with the clarity and detail of the sounds. Additionally, 25 out of 41 participants specifically reported that the “spatial positioning of sounds” was highly striking. Comments highlighting immersion, the three-dimensional sensation, and the feeling of being inside the sound stage also stood out (See Figure 14).

Figure 14. Reasons for Liking the Atmos Production

Overall, these survey findings indicate a clear interest in and a highly positive perception of Spatial Audio technology. As can be seen in the Likert Scale Score Distribution table below, responses to the questions, only a portion of which are shown on the left side of the table, were predominantly rated with the highest score (5), yielding largely positive outcomes. In particular, the high appreciation scores given to production-oriented questions reveal that the spatial audio experience offered by Dolby Atmos had a powerful and impressive impact on the listeners (See Figure 15). The fact that a considerable portion of the participants were individuals who are actively engaged in music suggests that the results reflect the perspectives of a group with a certain level of expertise and informed listening experience.

Figure 15. Likert Scale Score Distribution for the Atmos Listening Evaluation

Among the most appreciated aspects of Spatial Music were the strength of the spatial impression and the clarity/detail level of the sounds. Furthermore, the fact that the vast majority of participants preferred Dolby Atmos over stereo in a loudspeaker-based listening environment clearly demonstrated the potential of this format.

The data were thematically analysed based on open-ended participant feedback, and the results obtained through SPSS analysis were summarised at the end of the study. The listening experiences revealed comparative perceptual differences between the Atmos, stereo, and binaural formats.

8. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

This study makes a significant contribution to the existing literature and production practices by bringing the tradition of Turkish Folk Music (TFM) into dialogue with spatial audio technology and the Dolby Atmos format. By moving beyond conventional microphone techniques, the effort to create an immersive listening experience constitutes one of the study's most original aspects. Dolby Atmos is an object-based audio format that enables sound to be positioned not only along the horizontal plane but within a fully three-dimensional auditory environment. As noted by Boren (2017), the aesthetic placement of musical instruments within a three-dimensional soundstage constitutes one of the fundamental capabilities offered by this technology.

The ability of spatial audio technology to simulate natural acoustic environments has made it possible to present a genre with deep cultural roots, such as Turkish Folk Music, without disrupting its authentic character, while simultaneously offering a contemporary auditory aesthetic. This approach transforms the listener from a passive recipient of music into an active participant, positioning them as if they were a participant present within a "conversation" setting or a "communal circle" in which the performance traditionally takes place. In this respect, spatial audio provides a technological parallel to the collective and participatory nature inherent in Turkish Folk Music, representing a noteworthy artistic and aesthetic contribution.

8.1. Themes Emerging from Participant Feedback

Listener experiences related to stereo, Dolby Atmos, and headphone-based formats were evaluated through thematic analysis of qualitative data obtained via unstructured in-depth interviews. Based on participants' perceptual, emotional, and technical reflections, the spatial, aesthetic, and functional differences between the sound formats were categorised under distinct themes.

The findings indicate that the stereo format offers a more limited, front-focused, and familiar auditory field, whereas Dolby Atmos provides a more immersive, three-dimensional listening experience characterised by clearer instrumental separation, spatial distribution, and a stronger sense of depth. It was observed that Atmos mixes elicited physical orienting responses in listeners and generated a sensation of being "inside a live performance," particularly enhancing the perception of the soundstage in multi-instrumental arrangements. In terms of naturalness and perceived realism, the stereo format was described as more familiar due to established listening habits, while the level of detail and spatial organisation offered by Atmos was reported to enhance the sense of proximity to the performers and acoustic authenticity.

The vast majority of participants stated that Dolby Atmos does not compromise the performance of traditional Turkish Folk Music; on the contrary, it adds a new aesthetic and perceptual dimension to the performance. Atmos was regarded not only as a listening experience but also as a creative tool that enables rethinking recording, spatial placement, and compositional practices, particularly for traditional instruments such as members of the bağlama family.

Evaluations regarding listening environments and format preferences indicate that Dolby Atmos offers strong potential for leisure-oriented listening, particularly in home, in-car, and cinematic settings. In headphone-based listening, perceptual differences were observed between stereo and binaural formats; while some listeners described the binaural version as more surrounding and impressive, others reported that its clarity and detail were more limited compared to stereo. These variations were assessed to be related to individual listening habits, levels of technical perception, and the specific binaural settings used.

Overall, the findings demonstrate that spatial audio technologies represent not merely a technical innovation within the context of Turkish Folk Music but rather a multilayered potential capable of transforming listener perception, aesthetic experience, and production practices.

9. CONCLUSION

This study aimed to demonstrate how the traditional performance practices of Turkish Folk Music (TFM) can be reinterpreted through contemporary spatial audio technologies such as Dolby Atmos. Through the recording and mixing of the Erzurum-region folk piece "Uyan Sunam" in the Atmos format, the study reveals that TFM holds strong technical and aesthetic potential within a three-dimensional sound stage. By remaining faithful to the traditional musical structure, a balanced and controlled spatial mixing approach can be developed through contemporary production possibilities.

The recordings and listening tests conducted at the İTÜ MİAM studios indicated that Dolby Atmos mixes created a deeper, more surrounding, and immersive listening experience, demonstrating a clear preference trend over conventional stereo mixes. Participant feedback further suggests that spatial audio should be understood not merely as a technical innovation, but as a creative and expressive tool that enhances sensory and emotional engagement. The findings reveal that TFM instruments open up new areas for alternative performance practices and repertoire development within the context of spatial music, and that spatial audio technologies offer significant future-oriented potential at both academic and professional levels.

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